

Digital Skilling of Textile Artisans: Designing Smartphone Interfaces for Low-Literate Users

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Abstract:

Textile artisans with limited literacy often face barriers in adopting digital skilling tools, restricting their participation in the evolving technological landscape of textile production. This study explores how smartphone interface design can be optimized through visual affordances to support low-literate users. Using a human-centered design approach, the research involved ethnographic interviews, observational walkthroughs, and participatory co-design sessions with a Madhubani artisan from Maharashtra. Visual cues categorized as Discover, Look, and Go were analyzed and mapped within existing mobile interfaces to support task recognition, flow, and feedback. Key interface adaptations included the use of domain-specific iconography, minimal textual dependency, and consistent visual markers to enhance usability. These adaptations improved comprehension, engagement, and learning outcomes within digital skilling environments. The paper proposes a replicable design framework tailored for low-literate user groups in the textile sector, contributing to inclusive technology integration and skill-based economic resilience. Digital skilling empowers textile artisans by enhancing their access to markets, improving production efficiency, and fostering economic resilience in a rapidly digitizing industry.

Keywords: *artisan empowerment, digital skilling, inclusive interface, low-literate users, participatory design, visual affordance*

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1. Introduction

India's informal textile sector comprises over 7 million artisans, many of whom specialize in region-specific crafts such as Madhubani art and handloom weaving. Despite the rapid growth of mobile phone usage with rural mobile internet penetration crossing 37% in 2022, a significant portion of this population remains digitally excluded due to literacy-related barriers [1]. Government initiatives like Skill India, GeM, and ODOP aim to integrate artisans into mainstream markets and upskill them through mobile-first platforms. These platforms typically include mobile applications and web portals that offer access to training modules, product listing services, buyer-seller interactions, and digital payment systems. These schemes, while well-intentioned, often rely on text-heavy interfaces or English/Hindi-centric designs that are misaligned with the cognitive and linguistic realities of many rural users [2, 3 & 4].

While previous studies have explored digital access among rural populations, few have examined interface-level interactions from the standpoint of low-literate users especially within the fashion and textile artisan domain [5, 6]. This gap persists despite clear policy focus on digital inclusion and women-led entrepreneurship [6, 7 & 8]. Artisans increasingly rely on smartphones to source raw materials, follow craft tutorials, and connect with buyers. As a result, mobile interfaces have become a critical gateway to digital skilling and market participation. When artisans are unable to navigate digital tools independently, it leads to low

adoption rates, poor learning retention, and missed opportunities for growth. The digital divide becomes a design divide, particularly for women artisans who may already face social mobility constraints [7, 9].

This study addresses a critical usability barrier in the design of mobile interfaces for low-literate artisans. This study draws on the Visual Interaction Cues Framework, originally developed to guide users through complex digital environments. It adapts the framework's core concepts to smartphone interface design [4]. The framework outlines how visual cues such as layout emphasis, directional markers, and attention anchors can guide navigation, focus, and task initiation. These visual strategies are integrated within a human-centered design approach. This alignment connects interface logic with real-world artisan workflows and proposes practical alternatives for textile-focused digital ecosystems [3, 4]. The resulting visual framework-based interface model is intended for integration into skilling platforms that serve craft-based clusters. Additionally, the paper provides field-validated behavioral insights to support more inclusive UI/UX practices within textile technology applications [1, 9]. This paper bridges that gap and offer a tool for improving digital confidence, scalable interface strategy grounded in both visual affordance theory and artisan behaviour [1, 4].

2. Literature Review

The use of smartphones to support craft-based livelihoods has gained momentum in recent years, particularly within informal sectors such as textile production [5]. Mobile-based skilling platforms, digital marketplaces, and training applications have opened new avenues for artisans to learn, promote, and commercialize their work. However, many

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low-literate artisans particularly women in rural settings these opportunities are constrained by persistent usability challenges.

2.1 Smartphone Usage among Low-literate Artisans

Low-literate individuals, in the context of this study, are those whose formal education levels range between Standard Four and Standard Eight in the Indian State education system [6]. This group often includes skilled informal laborers and craft workers who, while lacking formal education, display strong manual and visual expertise [7]. Within the textile sector, artisans increasingly depend on smartphones to source materials, follow tutorials, and engage with buyers. However, their mental models based on tactile learning, analog workflows, and visual pattern recognition are often misaligned with abstract, text-heavy interface designs [2, 3]. This mismatch leads to low technology adoption, frequent task abandonment, and a lack of confidence in digital environments. Thus, the core challenge shifts from access to usability requiring visually intuitive, domain-specific, and cognitively lightweight design.

For the purpose of this study, the term low-literate users encompass two distinct groups:

- Low-literate individuals : Users who face difficulty reading, writing, and understanding short digital messages or instructions.
- Artisans : Skilled craftspeople engaged in traditional trades, often producing handcrafted goods using heritage techniques. Despite their expertise, many artisans struggle with digital literacy, particularly in interpreting abstract icons, navigating app hierarchies, and completing multi-step tasks.

In India, the Digital Empowerment Foundation [8] highlights how platforms like Skill India and GeM assume proficiency in Hindi or English, however users face challenges in changing language to their local language. Visual Cues are colour cues, shape cues and spatial cues, help in deeper understanding of how users learn and encode them. This includes ensuring the visibility of affordances, providing clear conceptual models, establishing natural mappings, and offering feedback for actions involving these elements. Visual cues help people understand and navigate technology in their everyday lives [9].

2.2 Visual Interaction Cues Framework (Adapted from Dillman's Framework [10])

This framework was originally proposed by as proposed by Dillman, Mok, Tang, Oehlberg, and Mitchell [10] in the context of video game environments and augmented reality. It systematically categorizes visual cues to support new users in navigating complex digital interfaces. Although designed for gaming, its emphasis on visual affordance and cue-based guidance makes it highly relevant for low-literate users in mobile-based skilling platforms. To analyze and structure visual interface design for low-literate users, this study

applies a visual interaction framework that categorizes cues across three dimensions: Task / Purpose, Markedness(Visual Affordance), and Trigger. This structured approach enables a deeper understanding of how interface elements influence user behavior and comprehension, particularly in low-literacy contexts. The current study adapts this framework to the context of textile artisans based on a literature review and field observations. Prior research has emphasized that low-literate users prefer visual interfaces over text-heavy designs, and that visual affordances such as color, size, and alignment significantly improve usability and task performance [11, 6 & 12].

2.2.1 Dimension 1: Task/Purpose

This dimension relates visual cues to user intent.

- Discover cues enable users to identify interactive elements, such as pulsating buttons or highlighted sections.
- Look cues draw sustained attention to critical areas through color contrast, animation, or motion.
- Go cues support task execution and flow, including directional arrows, breadcrumb trails, or progress indicators.

2.2.2 Dimension 2: Markedness

Markedness refers to the visual salience or prominence of interface cues.

- Subtle cues are softly integrated (e.g., notification dots) without breaking interface harmony.
- Emphasized cues use shadows, outlines, or color intensity to stand out.
- Integrated cues are embedded within existing elements (e.g., profile pictures in chat bubbles).
- Overlaid cues are layered above the interface (e.g., popups, tooltips, or banners).

2.2.3 Dimension 3: Trigger

This dimension classifies how cues are activated or surfaced.

- User-Triggered cues appear upon user interaction (e.g., tapping a thumbnail).
- Context-Triggered cues emerge based on environmental or behavioural context (e.g., location-based alerts).
- Agent-Triggered cues are system-driven responses, such as status messages or error prompts.
- Persistent cues are always visible to ensure ongoing guidance (e.g., sticky icons or top-bar menus).

This framework is particularly useful for evaluating mobile UI experiences for low-literate users, as it emphasizes visual comprehension over textual literacy and aligns closely with the workflows of non-traditional digital users such as rural artisans. The framework's three dimensions Task/Purpose, Markedness, and Trigger were refined through field

engagement and expert feedback, and their application is elaborated in the Methodology section.

3. Methodology

This study employed a human-centered design methodology using a qualitative case study approach. The research focused on a single artisan participant, Ranjana Chaudhary a Madhubani artist and community art trainer based in Palghar district, Maharashtra. Fieldwork was conducted between January and March 2024 in her semi-urban artisan cluster. While the study centered on Ranjana and her learners, this choice was intentional to allow for deep contextual immersion and iterative design feedback. Ranjana was selected through purposive sampling due to her active engagement in traditional textile arts and her representative digital experience. A supplementary group of ten artisan learners attending her community-based training sessions provided comparative insights across experience levels. The findings are not intended to be generalized across all Indian textile arts but rather to inform design principles for similar low-literacy artisan contexts.

A three-phase iterative design process was adopted.

- Phase 1 – Contextual Inquiry: Ethnographic interviews and observational studies were conducted to understand Ranjana's digital behavior, mental models, and interface challenges.
- Phase 2 – Co-Design Exploration: Participatory workshops were organized to explore visual cue preferences using card sorting and prototype walkthroughs with 10 artisans.

The study focused on how visual affordances icons, layout, color, and image metaphors can support task navigation for users with limited literacy. Ranjana, who occasionally receives orders via WhatsApp but has minimal exposure to structured digital skilling platforms, was selected through purposive sampling for her active involvement in traditional textile arts and her representative digital experience.

In addition to the core case study, the research included a supplementary session with ten artisan learners (Fig. 1, center), who attend Ranjana's community-based training classes. This extended participant group provided

comparative insights on interface predictability and cue interpretation across experience levels

The integration of field-based observations, visual feedback, and cue testing provided rich qualitative data for analyzing how low-literate artisans interact with mobile interfaces in the context of textile training and production.

3.1 Data Collection Methods

Three qualitative methods were used to gather insights from the participants:

- Ethnographic Interviews: Conducted in Hindi and Marathi over five sessions, these interviews explored Ranjana Chaudhary's daily routines, her perceptions of smartphone-based platforms, and past experiences with digital self-skilling attempts.
- Participatory Design Exercises: Structured design workshops with 10 artisans including Ranjana Chaudhary were held in two iterative loops, including:
- Visual Cue Reviews: Stimuli boards were prepared using a mix of realistic images, hand-drawn illustrations, and clipart styles. These were printed and laminated for tactile interaction during workshops
- WhatsApp-Based Interface Analysis: Sample conversations involving order placement, image sharing, and payment queries were used to observe icon recognition and action predictability.
- YouTube Tutorials: Commonly accessed videos such as “Madhubani Art for Beginners” and “Handmade Textile Techniques” were used to study navigation behavior and cue interpretation. These were selected based on participant recall and viewing history.

Each activity was repeated with feedback validation to finalize the participant's preferences on navigation flow, visual structure, and interface clarity. All activities were documented through field notes, audio recordings, and photo captures. Observations were systematically categorized using the Visual Interaction Cues Framework by Dillman, Mok, Tang, Oehlberg, and Mitchell [10] and validated through participant feedback loops.

Figure 1: Left: Ranjana Chaudhary, Madhubani artist and art trainer. Centre: Artisan student showcasing artwork.

3.2 Ethical Considerations

Informed verbal consent was obtained prior to all field sessions. The participant was briefed on the research purpose and data usage. All recordings and photographs were made with explicit permission. Participation was scheduled around her professional hours, and all data were anonymized for publication. Identity disclosure, where applicable, was included only with written consent.

4. Results

The findings from this case study are organized into three thematic clusters derived from the Visual Interaction Cues Framework: Discover, Look, and Go. These themes capture how the participant, Ranjana Chaudhary a Madhubani artisan engaged with mobile-based applications, particularly WhatsApp and YouTube, in the context of skilling, content access, and task navigation. The analysis is based on observational sessions, co-design exercises, and post-task interviews.

4.1 Visual Cue Reviews: Style and Predictability

To evaluate how different graphic styles influence visual recognition and navigational accuracy, a card-sorting activity was conducted with 10 artisans, including Ranjana Chaudhary. Visual elements were grouped into three categories real-life photographs (Figure 1), clipart illustrations (Figure 2), and black-and-white abstract icons (Figure 3) each depicting textile-related tasks such as stocking, sourcing, and selling.

The purpose of this comparison was to assess which style of visual representation was most effective and accurate for low-literate artisan users, rather than to compare identical content. While the visual styles were standardized to represent similar tasks, some inconsistencies in contextual relevance were noted. For example, the photograph depicted a saree store, the clipart showed a modern apparel outlet, and the icon resembled a fruit shop. These mismatches were acknowledged during participant feedback and are considered a limitation in stimuli design. However, the comparative exercise successfully revealed that real-life photographs consistently enabled clearer recognition, emotional relevance, and task confidence, validating their superiority for UI design in artisan contexts.

Across participants, real-life photographs emerged as the most recognizable and confidently interpreted. Images showing fabric stacks, stitched materials, or close-up work (e.g., hands embroidering) were quickly associated with known tasks from their daily practice. One artisan remarked that “pictures with people doing the work help me understand what to press.” Clipart illustrations, while visually distinct, often led to partial or incorrect interpretations. Retail storefronts were sometimes understood, but abstract characters or generic scenes such as a suited figure holding papers were misinterpreted as unrelated actions like “school admissions” or “bank work.” Black-and-white abstract icons were consistently the least effective. Icons representing stalls, warehouses, or interactions lacked emotional

Figure 2: Clipart illustrations

Figure 3: Black-and-white abstract icons

relevance and were frequently ignored or misunderstood. As one participant noted, “flat pictures don't tell me what is happening.”

Quantitative Support: Among the 10 artisan participants:

- • 9 preferred real-life photographs
- • 6 partially understood clipart illustrations
- • All 10 misinterpreted or ignored abstract icons

These findings confirmed that predictability and interpretability in UI visuals increase significantly when images are grounded in real-world, domain-specific context. To ensure contextual validity, all tested elements drew from familiar textile metaphors tailoring tools, artisan workflows, and WhatsApp interactions previously identified as highly intuitive by the artisan participants. For users operating in hands-on, visually grounded environments like textile craft, realism not abstraction is critical for clarity, confidence, and task completion.

4.2 WhatsApp-Mapped Visual Affordance Framework

Following the card-sorting activity, participants engaged in an interface walkthrough using WhatsApp, identified as the most familiar and frequently used application among all 10 artisan participants. This exercise involved mapping interface elements such as icons, screen layouts, and interaction flows, against a structured visual interaction framework. The goal was to assess how users respond to real-world mobile navigation, focusing on how visual cues support comprehension and task execution in low-literacy contexts.

Task-Purpose Dimension

Visual cues were observed in relation to three dominant user purposes:

- **Discover Cues:** Participants relied more on color, shape, and spatial position than textual labels to identify clickable elements. Familiar indicators, like the double tick mark for message delivery, were consistently recognized across all users. Highlighted sections within the interface played a key role in helping participants distinguish categories and understand functionality, especially in visually complex layouts [13].
- **Look Cues:** Real-time animations (e.g., “typing...” indicators) and high-contrast visuals maintained user attention and signalled interaction continuity. These cues were most effective when supported by consistent visual patterns and emotional relevance. These mirrored real-time feedback such as changing red prompts, and animated overlays were used to warn users of high-risk events [14].
- **Go Cues:** Directional symbols like green call buttons or paper plane icons enabled task execution due to their

metaphorical familiarity. However, unfamiliar or ambiguous icons introduced hesitation. Prior studies support this by advocating breadcrumb trails, tick marks, and visual confirmations to boost confidence during action-taking.

- These observed patterns reinforce the idea that purpose-driven visual cues play a critical role in enhancing navigation clarity and supporting user decision-making. By aligning interface elements with user intent, designers can create more intuitive and accessible digital experiences, particularly for audiences with limited literacy.

Markedness Dimension

Visual cues were further categorized by their importance:

- **Subtle Cues:** WhatsApp's small notification dots served as gentle indicators of unread messages, similar to softly glowing markers in language-learning apps. For instance, a soft-glow icon next to new vocabulary words to signal review actions without disrupting interface consistency [15].
- **Emphasized Cues:** Red alert badges for missed calls or messages were highly effective in capturing user attention. Similarly, the use of bold outlines around active icons within task sequences helped guide focus and support decision-making, demonstrating how visual emphasis can enhance interface usability [16].
- **Integrated Cues:** Embedded elements, such as profile images within chat threads, supported user recognition.
- **Overlaid Cues:** Features like call banners or popups prompted time-sensitive responses. These layered visuals proved successful in enhancing task urgency and preventing missed actions.

Among these, integrated and Overlaid cues not explored while designing UI for low-literate users.

Trigger/Action Dimension

Cues were examined for how they were activated:

- **User-Triggered:** Actions like tapping on WhatsApp statuses or YouTube thumbnails showed that participants were most comfortable with direct, touch-based interaction. These cues reinforced user confidence and task independence.
- **Context-Triggered, Agent-Triggered, and Persistent Cues:** These were either minimally used or rarely noticed by participants. System-generated prompts, time-based triggers, or static icons did not significantly influence user behavior indicating limited engagement with non-direct cues in current usage patterns.

User-triggered cues such as tapping on WhatsApp statuses or YouTube thumbnails emerged as the most effective interaction pattern. Research confirms that tap-based interactions, especially when coupled with simplified screens and familiar icons, enhance accessibility for low-literate users [2]. In contrast, context-triggered, agent-triggered, and persistent cues were relatively underutilized in mainstream applications, despite their potential to provide timely guidance and reduce user errors. Broader integration of these cues could substantially support digital independence among low-literate populations.

These findings align with existing insights in human-computer interaction, highlighting the importance of inclusive design cues in guiding user attention within complex interfaces [17]. Emphasizing visual elements during the discovery phase, such as breadcrumb trails, culturally familiar icons, and responsive feedback has been shown to significantly improve navigation for non-literate users [3, 13]. Additionally, visual indicators like color-coded arrows in mobile financial tools can effectively replace textual instructions for semi-literate audiences [13]. Cues such as “Look” and “Go” have also been found to encourage independent action among low-literate users in digital advisory platforms [18].

Unlike previous work that isolates visual interventions to specific screens or functions, this study integrates cue-based design across the complete task flow. It demonstrates that domain-relevant and context-specific visuals especially photographs and tactile metaphors are not only more intuitive but also essential for task execution and trust-building among low-literate textile artisans.

5. Discussion

Field-Validating Visual Affordances in Textile Technology
This study applies a visual interaction framework within a real-world textile skilling context, moving beyond theoretical exploration through direct field validation. The use of domain-relevant visuals such as tailoring tools, process-based photographs, and WhatsApp interface elements grounds the interface design in practical, artisan-centered use cases. The integration of domain-relevant visuals such as textile tools, craft photographs, and WhatsApp-based interaction mapping anchors the interface model in real-world use cases. Furthermore, the combined

ethnography and co-design methodology enhances both contextual relevance and transferability. By aligning findings with visual affordance theory, the study contributes replicable design insights for inclusive textile skilling platforms. The combination of ethnographic fieldwork and co-design workshops provided deep contextual insights while allowing for iterative testing. These findings not only reinforce visual affordance theory but also demonstrate replicability for interface design in other textile skilling contexts. While the findings reinforce visual affordance theory, the practical application and replication of these insights require clearer task-level recommendations. To address this, future work will detail specific UI actions such as image forwarding, group management, and location sharing that artisans perform on smartphones, along with corresponding visual design strategies.

6. Conclusion

This study investigated how low-literate textile artisans interact with smartphone interfaces, specifically WhatsApp, to evaluate the role of visual affordances in digital navigation. By applying a structured visual interaction framework, the research examined how the function, prominence, and activation of visual cues influence user engagement and comprehension. Field-based participatory co-design revealed that domain-specific visuals such as realistic photographs and metaphor-driven icons significantly enhance task orientation and user confidence. Emphasized and spatially consistent cues were found to support intuitive navigation, while persistent and context-sensitive triggers improved usability and learning in mobile skilling environments.

By grounding interface design in the behaviors and cognitive patterns of artisans, the study presents a replicable and technically sound framework for inclusive UI development in the textile sector. These findings contribute to more effective digital onboarding, self-skilling, and commercial participation among low-literate artisan communities, supporting broader goals of inclusive growth within the Indian textile economy. Although this study focused on visual elements, it acknowledges that text and language options remain critical. Future iterations will explore the balance between visual and textual content, especially in multilingual contexts where English/Hindi-centric designs may not align with user realities.

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